

Synthesis of Some Novel β -lactam Derivatives

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One oxa-dethiacepham derivative containing one fused and one isolated β -lactam moieties has been synthesised utilizing the ketene-imine reaction and (2 + 2) cycloaddition of CSI to olefin. The synthesis of three novel tricyclic di- β -lactam derivatives is also reported. The bicyclic and tricyclic β -lactam derivatives have been characterised by ir and nmr spectral data and some by mass spectral data.

THE biological activity of the β -lactam antibiotic is generally believed to be associated with the chemical reactivity of their β -lactam ring which in turn is thought to be dependent on the tail end (amide side chain) as well as on the head of the antibiotic molecule¹.

Initially, most of the research program was concerned with the modification of the tail end which lead to the introduction of a large number of clinically useful penam and cepham derivatives².

Subsequently, special attention was focussed on the modification of the head of the antibiotic molecule. Replacements of sulphur atom of these bicyclic compounds by carbon^{3,4}, nitrogen⁵ or oxygen^{6,7} were carried out in order to enhance the reactivity of azetidione carbonyl function and consequently the antibacterial activity. Various ring homologues⁸ have also been synthesised with similar objective. A recent report⁹ describes the synthesis of a novel biologically active compound (II) obtained by introducing a third hetero atom in place of C₃ of cephalosporin. More recently, some workers in this field got interested in the synthesis of compounds containing more than one β -lactam ring¹⁰⁻¹⁵.

Prompted by the synthesis of novel aza-analogue of cepham by Wolfe *et al*¹⁶, Bose and coworkers¹⁷ have recently communicated the total synthesis of some analogous compounds. They have successfully synthesised a number of 1-azadethiacepham derivative (III) by the 'acid chloride-imine' method.

However, their attempt to synthesise 1-azadethiacepham derivative (IV) from phenylimidazoline with azidoacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine did not meet with desired success¹⁷. The failure of isolation of the penam analogue in pure form was attributed to the striking decrease in stability in going from 1-azadethiacepham to the corresponding penam series.

Since β -amino- β -lactams are unstable¹⁸ because of participation of N-p-electrons in the ring opening reactions, we thought of synthesising the above penam analogue by blocking this participation through amidification of the imidazoline derivative.

Reaction of 2-phenyl-imidazoline with phenoxyacetyl chloride in presence of barium carbonate gave amide (VI) in good yield. The product was characterised by ir and nmr spectral data. [IR (CHCl₃): 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide, carbonyl), 1620 cm⁻¹ (imine function). NMR(CDCl₃) δ : 3.6 (m, 4H), 4.45 (s, 2H), 6.9-7.8 (m, 10H) ppm].

The amide (VI) on reacting with further amount of phenoxyacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine gave a semi solid mass, which resisted crystallization. The ir spectra not only affords an easy way of distinguishing between structure (V) and (VI)

but also between the structure (VI) and (VII). An open chain tertiary amide carbonyl group generally absorbs in the region $1650-1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [(VI)- 1660 cm^{-1}]. In (VII) where the amide carbonyl group is part of a fused ring system, the $\nu\text{ C=O}$ is shifted, as expected, to a much lower wave length (1785 cm^{-1}). The other peak, 1660 cm^{-1} , in the double bond region is attributed to the open chain amide carbonyl function. The assignment of the structure was further supported by the absence of a peak at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N function).

Attempts at purification of the compound, however, led to its decomposition to amide (VI) as characterised by m.m.p. and ir spectra.

Since 1-aza- and 1-oxadethiacepham derivatives are readily obtainable from tetrahydropyrimidines¹⁷ and dihydrooxazines¹⁹ respectively, and since many of them are reported to be biologically active, it was thought of interest to synthesise a novel derivative (X) containing one more β -lactam ring. Our choice of preparing 1-oxadethiacepham was guided by the knowledge that replacement of sulphur atom at position 1 of the cepham nucleus with oxygen enhances the biological activity^{20,21}.

For building up the second β -lactam ring we utilized the cyclo-addition reaction between chlorosulphonyl isocyanate (CSI) and olefin (IX). The (2+2) cyclo-addition of CSI to olefins to produce β -lactams is a well documented reaction²²⁻²⁴.

Oxazines (VIII) (2-alkenyl-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-5,6-dihydro-1,3-oxazine) were readily obtained from the reaction between commercially available 2-methyl-2,4-pentandiol with unsaturated nitriles²⁵.

Compound	IR	NMR (CDCl ₃) (δ) ppm	Mass spectra
IXa : R = Ph (β -lactam)	1760 cm^{-1}	1.35-1.8(m, 11H), 4.2(m, 1H), 5.0(s 1H), 6.2-6.5(m, 2H), 6.8-7.4(m, 10H)	363(M ⁺), 335, 295, 305, 229
IXb : R = H (β -lactam)	1760 cm^{-1}	1.35-1.8(m, 11H) 4.2(m, 1H) 4.9(s, 1H) 5.2-6.2(m, 3H), 6.8-7.4(m, 5H)	287(M ⁺), 259, 229, 153

These derivatives, after usual characterisation, were reacted with phenoxyacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in methylene chloride solution at 0° . The isolated β -lactams, obtained in about 70% yield were characterised by ir, nmr and mass spectral data.

The mass fragmentation pattern is explained as under :

The reaction of CSI with the above fused β -lactam-oxazolidine derivative (IX) gave the N-chlorosulphonyl- β -lactam (XI).

Reductive hydrolysis followed by immediate amidification of the N-unsubstituted β -lactam gave the desired compound in 30-35% overall yield based on oxazine derivative (IX). The di-lactam (X) was a viscous semisolid mass giving a single spot on tlc and showed infrared absorptions at 1775 cm^{-1} (fused β -lactam carbonyl), 1750 (isolated β -lactam carbonyl) and 1685 cm^{-1} (amide carbonyl). The nmr spectrum is also in agreement with the assigned structure. NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.2-1.5(m, 11H), 4.2(m, 1H), 4.5-5.2(m, 5H), 6.8-8.4(m, 15H) ppm.

The reaction of CSI with (IXb), however, met with failure.

It is interesting to note here that the β -hydrogen atom of an imine often plays an important role in the 'ketene-imine' reaction. The oxazine derivative (XII) obtained from 2-methyl-2,4-pentandiol and cyanoacetic ester²⁵, on reaction with acid chloride-triethylamine gave the amide (XIII) rather than the β -lactam derivative (XIV).

The amides (XIII) were characterised by ir, nmr and mass spectral data. IR (CHCl₃): 1710 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O), 1680 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O).

The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak M⁺ 349 (for XIIIa). The singlet (2H) in nmr at 4.8 ppm is attributed to the phenoxy methylene proton. The other protons appear at their usual places. NMR (CDCl₃) δ: 1.1-1.8 (m, 14H), 4.1 (q, 2H), 4.4(m, 1H), 4.8(s, 2H), 6.7-7.2(m, 6H) ppm.

Bose *et al*²⁶ had also faced a similar practical problem in their attempt to synthesise exocyclic thio-analogue of penicillins and cephalosporins. The alkyl thio-group in the imine portion helped in the isomerisation of double bond resulting in the formation of unsaturated amide (XV).

In an attempt to rectify the situation, we tried to react the imine (XII) with preformed phenoxyketene (reported stable)²⁷, to preclude isomerisation under basic condition. We were, however, unsuccessful in obtaining the phenoxy-ketene in pure form and the crude material failed to react with imine under the experimental conditions used.

The synthesis of some 3-azacephalosporins was first reported in 1980 by Mashimoto and coworkers⁹. The insignificant antibiotic activity of these compounds was attributed to the instability of the unsaturated molecule, for these compounds when reduced to 3-azacephams by Al/Hg in aqueous THF, were found to be biologically active.

The above observations coupled with easy access to thiadiazines, led us to synthesise some novel tricyclic-di-β-lactam derivatives.

2,6-diphenyl-4,4-dimethyl-4H-1,3,5-thiadiazine (XVI) was prepared by slightly modifying the method developed by Giordanco and coworkers²⁸ involving condensation of thiabenzamide, acetone and benzonitrile in presence of borontri-

fluoroetherate. The yield of the product obtained by us was higher than the reported value.

When thiadiazine (XVI) was reacted with equimolar quantity of azido-acetyl chloride in methylene chloride at 0°, the azacepham [XVII: 2,2-dimethyl-4,6-diphenyl-7-azido-8-oxo-5-thia-1,3-diazabicyclo-(4,2,0)-3-octene] was obtained as the major product (70% yield). The compound (XVIII) was also isolated from the reaction mixture as a minor product (15% yield).

The structure of compound (XVII) was established by ir, nmr and mass spectral data as well as by elemental analysis.

The ir peaks at 2100, 1770, 1620 cm⁻¹ are attributed to azido, β-lactam-carbonyl and imine functions respectively.

The nmr spectrum is also in agreement with the assigned structure. NMR (CDCl₃) δ: 1.3(s, 3H), 2.0(s, 3H), 5.0(s, 1H), 7.4(m, 8H), 7.9(m, 2H) ppm.

The gem dimethyl groups of thiadiazine (XVI) appear as a singlet (6H) at δ: 1.65 ppm. It is interesting to note that the gem dimethyl group of the product (XVII) appear as two singlets, one at δ: 1.3(3H) and the other at δ: 2.00(3H) because of the non-equivalence of gem dimethyl protons in the product.

Though the mass spectrum failed to show the molecular ion²⁹, the compound was well characterised by (M-N₂)⁺ peak and the following fragmentation pattern.

Our objective in using azido-acetyl chloride in above annelation reaction was to utilize the azido function to provide different amide chains at the desired position of the molecule. It has been established earlier that the β-lactam function is stable to the reagents needed to convert an azide to an amide via an amine. The products incidentally also helped in further characterisations of the cepham analogues.

The conversion of an azido-derivative (XVII) to 7-benzamidocepham [XIX: 2,2-dimethyl-4,6-diphenyl-7-benzamido-8-oxo-5-thia-1,3-diazabicyclo-(4,2,0)-3-octene] was carried out in the usual fashion^{30,31}. Reduction with H₂S-Et₃N gave an amine which was coupled, without isolation, with benzoyl chloride-triethylamine to give the desired product in fairly good yield (65%).

The ir peaks at 3400, 1765, 1670 and 1620 cm^{-1} are attributed to N-H, β -lactam carbonyl, amide carbonyl and amine functions respectively.

The nmr spectrum shows the following pattern. NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 1.45(s, 3H), 2.00(s, 3H), 5.85(d, 1H), 7.0-8.0(m, 16H) ppm.

The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak at 441. Some of the fragments are explained as under :

When thiadiazine (XVI) was treated with 2.2 moles of azido-acetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine, the compound [XVIII : 2,2-dimethyl-5,9-diazido-6,8-diphenyl-4,10-dioxo-1,3-diaza-7-thiatricyclo-(6,2,0,0^{a,e})-decane] was obtained in 65-70% yield.

The ir spectrum shows peaks at 2100, 1790 and 1770 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the azido and the two β -lactam carbonyl functions.

It is worthwhile to mention here that the gem dimethyl groups again appear as a singlet at δ : 2.0(6H) as a result of recreation of identical environment for the methyl protons in this molecule.

The nmr spectra show the following pattern. NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 2.00 (s, 6H) 4.4 (s, 2H), 7.5 (s, 10H) ppm.

As is common to many azido-derivatives²⁹, this compound also does not show the molecular ion peak but gives (M-56)⁺ peak²⁹. The fragmentation pattern is explained as under :

The compound (XVII) was reduced with $\text{H}_2\text{S-Et}_3\text{N}$ in methylene chloride to the diamino derivative which was amidified with three different acid chloride under basic conditions. The products (XXa, XXb, XXc) were characterised by ir and nmr spectra and elemental analysis.

Compound	IR spectrum	NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm
XXa	3400, 1770, 1750, 1670 cm^{-1}	2,1(s, 6H), 5.4(m, 2H), 6.0(d, 2H), 7.2-7.7(m, 2OH)
XXb	3370, 1770, 1750, 1680 cm^{-1}	1.9(s, 6H), 3.2(s, 4H), 5.1(d, 1H), 5.4(d, 1H), 6.7-7.5(m, 522H)
XXc	3370, 1770, 1755, 1690 cm^{-1}	2,1(s, 6H), 4.2(q, 4H)*, 5.3(d, 2H) 6.5-7.6(m, 22H)

*The methylene protons (Ph-OCH_2) appears as a quartet. This type of non equivalence of methylene protons are known in the literature³².

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Pet. ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60-80°.

(a) 2,2,4-trimethyl-6-(β -styryl)-5-oxa-7-phenoxy-8-oxo-1-azabicyclo-(4,2,0)-octane (IX) : A solution of VIII (2.3 g ; 0.01 mole) and triethylamine (1.35 ml) in 40 ml dry methylene chloride was cooled to 0°. To this was added dropwise with stirring, phenoxyacetyl chloride (1.75 g ; 0.01 mole) in 15 ml methylene chloride and the stirring was continued overnight at room temperature. The mixture was washed with water, then with 10% aqueous NaHCO_3 solution and again with water. The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 . Removal of solvent afforded a solid residue, which was crystallized with pet. ether/methylene chloride to give white crystalline solid (2.8 g ; 70%) m.p. 132°. IR(CHCl_3) 1760 cm^{-1} (β -lactam C=O) ; nmr (CDCl_3) δ : 1.35-1.8 (m, 11H), 4.2 (m, 1H), 5.0 (s, 1H), 6.2-6.5 (m, 2H), 6.8-7.4 (m, 10H) ppm. ; MS - M^+ 363, 335, 305 etc. Found : C, 75.85 ; H, 7.11 ; N, 3.62. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_5$; C, 76.00 ; H, 6.93 ; N, 3.85%.

(b) 2,2,4-trimethyl-6-(N' -phenoxyacetyl-2'-oxo-4'-phenyl-3'-azetidiny-)-5-oxa-7-phenoxy-8-oxo-1-azabicyclo-(4,2,0)-octane (X) : To a solution of IXa (1.81 g ; 0.005 mole) in 50 ml dry methylene chloride was added dropwise with stirring CSI (0.71 g ; 0.005 mole) in 10 ml methylene chloride at -20°. The stirring was continued for 1 hr at -20°, and then another hr at 4°. The methylene chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was added dropwise to a stirred mixture of Na_2SO_8 (10 ml, 25%) in ether (20 ml) maintained at 0°. The aqueous layer was made slightly alkaline by adding dilute potassium hydroxide solution. The organic layer was removed and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (20 ml x 3). The combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 . The residue, obtained on removing the solvent, was redissolved in 10 ml dry methylene chloride, cooled to 0° and mixed with triethylamine (0.5 g). To this was added dropwise, with stirring phenoxyacetyl chloride (0.85 g ; 0.005 mole) in 10 ml methylene chloride. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hr at room temperature. The mixture was washed with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and again with water. The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 . The

solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed over silica using pet. ether/methylene chloride (50 : 50) as eluent to yield a viscous semisolid mass (0.8 g; 30%) giving single spot on tlc. IR (CHCl₃): 1775 cm⁻¹ (fused β-lactam C=O) 1750 cm⁻¹ (monocyclic β-lactam C=O), 1685 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 1.2-1.5 (m, 11H), 4.2 (m, 1H), 4.5-5.2 (m, 5H), 6.8-8.4 (m, 15H) ppm. Found : C, 71.32; H, 5.76; N, 5.32. Calcd. for C₃₂H₃₂N₂O₈; C, 71.09; H, 5.96; N, 5.18%.

(c) 2,2-dimethyl-4,6-diphenyl-7-azido-8-oxo-5-thia-1,3-diazabicyclo-(4,2,0)-3-octene (XVII) : A solution of thiadiazine (XVI) (2.8 g; 0.01 mole) and triethylamine (1.35 ml) in 60 ml dry methylene chloride was cooled to 0°. To this was added, with stirring over a period of 30 min, a solution of azidoacetyl chloride (1.2 g; 0.01 mole) in 20 ml of methylene chloride. The mixture was stirred for 1 hr at 0° and then 2 hr at room temperature. The reaction mixture was thoroughly washed with water. The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄. Removal of solvent afforded a brown residue which when chromatographed over silica using ether/methylene chloride (40 : 60) as eluent gave first a solid crystalline material (XVII) (2.5 g; 70%, m.p. 119°) and then XVIII (0.5 g; 15%, m.p. 160° decomp.). IR (XVII) (CDCl₃): 2100 cm⁻¹ (azido), 1770 cm⁻¹ (β-lactam C=O), 1620 cm⁻¹ (—C=N); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 1.3 (s, 3H), 2.0 (s, 3H), 5.0 (s, 1H), 7.4 (m, 8H), 7.9 (m, 2H) ppm; MS 335 (M⁺-28) 320, 308. Found : C, 62.93; H, 4.87; N, 19.45. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₇N₅O₅; C, 62.79; H, 4.71; N, 19.27%.

(d) 2,2-dimethyl-4,6-diphenyl-7-benzamido-8-oxo-5-thia-1,3-diazabicyclo-(4,2,0)-3-octene (XIX) : H₂S was bubbled into a solution of XVII (1.1 g; 0.003 mole) in 40 ml methylene chloride containing triethylamine (0.6 ml) for 10 min at 0°. After stirring 1 hr the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue sucked dry under high vacuum.

The crude amine was redissolved in 30 ml dry methylene chloride and cooled to 0° and was mixed with triethylamine (0.5 ml). To this was added dropwise with stirring, benzoyl chloride (0.450 g) in 10 ml methylene chloride. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hr at room temperature. It was then washed with water, 10% aqueous NaHCO₃ solution and finally with water. The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄. Removal of solvent and crystallisation of the residue with pet. ether/methylene chloride gave white crystalline material (0.8 g; 65%, m.p. 181°). IR (CHCl₃): 3400 cm⁻¹ (N—H), 1765 cm⁻¹ (β-lactam C=O), 1670 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O), 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 1.45 (s, 3H), 2.00 (s, 3H), 5.85 (d, 1H), 7.0-8.0 (m, 16H) ppm; MS 441, 281, 161. Found : C, 70.57; H, 5.34; N, 9.33. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₃N₃O₂S; C, 70.72; H, 5.25; N, 9.52%.

(e) 2,2-dimethyl-6,8-diphenyl-5,9-diazido-4,10-dioxo-1,3-diaza-7-thiatricyclo-(6,2,0,0^{3,6}) decane (XVIII) : The compound was obtained on treatment of thiadiazine (2.8 g) with 2.2 molar ratio of the azido-acetyl chloride and working up as before

(see experiment-c). Yield (3.1 g; 65%, m.p. 160° decomp). IR (CHCl₃): 2100 cm⁻¹ (azido), 1790 cm⁻¹, 1770 cm⁻¹ (β-lactam C=O); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 2.0 (s, 6H), 4.4 (s, 2H), 7.3 (m, 10H) ppm. MS 390 (M⁺-56), 335, 320, 280 etc. Found : C, 56.31; H, 4.13; N, 25.17. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₈N₈O₂S; C, 56.49; H, 4.06; N, 25.09%.

(g) 2,2-dimethyl-6,8-diphenyl-5,9-diphenylacetamido-4,8-dioxo-1,3-diaza-7-thiatricyclo-(6,2,0,0^{3,6}) decane (XXb) : Yield 70%, m.p. 212° (decomp). IR (CHCl₃): 3370 cm⁻¹ (N—H), 1770, 1750 cm⁻¹ (β-lactam C=O), 1685 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 1.9 (s, 6H), 3.2 (s, 4H), 5.1 (d, 1H), 5.4 (d, 1H), 6.7-7.5 (m, 22H) ppm. Found : C, 70.18; H, 5.52; N, 8.76. Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₄N₄O₄S; C, 70.45; H, 5.35; N, 8.83%.

(h) 2,2-dimethyl-6,8-diphenyl-5,9-diphenylacetamido-4,8-dioxo-7-thia-1,3-diazatricyclo-(6,2,0,0^{3,6}) decane (XXc) : Yield 70%, m.p. 196° (decomp). IR (CHCl₃): 3370 cm⁻¹ (N—H), 1770 cm⁻¹-1755 cm⁻¹ (β-lactam C=O), 1690 (amide C=O); nmr (CDCl₃) δ : 2.1 (s, 6H), 4.2 (q, 4H), 5.3 (d, 2H), 6.5-7.6 (m, 22H) ppm. Found : C, 66.97; H, 5.02; N, 8.49. Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₄N₄O₆S; C, 67.05; H, 5.17; N, 8.45%.

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